

CLEWS model for India: Urbanisation and Rooftop solar scenarios

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Executive Summary

Energy, land, and water systems in India were modelled to assess urbanisation and energy decentralisation scenarios from years 2020 to 2070. The business as usual (BAU) finds that energy costs are expected to rise, due primarily to contribution from nuclear power. Furthermore, food demand is expected to double in 2070. Rapid urbanisation scenarios point to increasing deforestation, strain on water resources mainly driven by food and public water demand. Energy decentralisation scenarios suggest partial replacement of nuclear fuel with rooftop solar.

The policy recommendations for India are-

1. Invest in agricultural technologies to improve yields, irrigation technologies for optimum use of water.
2. Deploy rooftop solar aggressively to mitigate higher energy costs in future.

1. Introduction:

India finds itself in a unique situation in a way that it is a country with highest population in the world, currently experiencing rapid industrial growth, while being largely agrarian economy. As seen in figure 1(a), increasing public demand and rapid industrialisation have led to around 7% year on year (YoY) increase in power generation. At the same time, water scarcity (Figure 1(b)), and agricultural implications, together with increasing urbanisation, threaten to leave large section of population vulnerable to climate change. This means that India's growing energy demand while managing limited water and land resources requires careful policy formulation. This study aims to observe impact of rapid urbanisation on water and land resources. Furthermore, study explores energy decentralisation as means of energy inclusion while reducing carbon footprint.

Figure 1. (a) Percentage increase in energy demand in India [1] and (b) population growth impact on per capita water availability in India [2].

2. Methodology:

To assess intricate co-dependencies of energy, land and water systems, OSeMOSYS [3] tool was used with integrated CLEWs framework [4]. All the key energy inputs for model for India, including but not limited to (a) Energy mix (b) power generation capacity (c) energy costs (d) efficiency (e) operation life is taken from CCG starter data kit. Land availability data is sourced from Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [5, 6]. Water related data is sourced from [7]. The links between the data are created according to 'Reference CLEWs Diagram' shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Reference CLEWS diagram for India

After baseline model, also referred to as Business as usual (BAU), was established, Two scenarios were created sequentially, i.e. on top of previous scenario, namely (1) Urbanisation (S1) and (2) Energy decentralisation through rooftop solar (S2). To reflect urbanisation scenario in model, the energy demand, built up land, public water demand, crops demand was increased by up to 1.5% YoY with respect to BAU. Finally, to reflect energy decentralisation i.e. rapid solar rooftop adoption, in the model, existing capacity of 10 GW was compounded at 10% YoY until 2070 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Baseline scenario (BAU), followed by urbanisation and rooftop solar scenarios built sequentially (i.e. on top of the previous) along with the accompanying key assumptions.

3. Results:

3.1. Baseline model:

Energy demand is largely fulfilled by coal, biomass and hydro until 2040. However, the future demand is primarily met by nuclear fuel (150,000 PJ in 2070) (Figure 4(a)). This is possibly due to relatively lower operation life of hydro (30 years), biomass (30 years) compared to nuclear power (60 years). However, nuclear power comes at a steep capital cost (Figure 4(b)) and overall cost of energy (Figure 4(c)). Large component of overall cost of energy ((Figure 4(b)) comes from capital costs, clearly due to high capital costs for nuclear power.

Figure 4. (a) Energy production by competing fuel sources showing around 7% growth (b) Capital costs of power plants and (c) overall cost of energy generation (Fixed + variable + Capital)

The crop demand and water demand for base model is shown in figure 5 (a) and (b), showing two fold and three fold increase respectively in 2070.

Figure 5. Baseline projections from 2020-2070 for (a) crop demand and (b) water demand, respectively.

3.2. Urbanisation Scenario:

The urbanisation scenario was analysed by plotting the difference S1 and BAU to observe interconnectedness of energy (figure 6(a)), land (figure 6(b, c and d)) and water (figure 6(e)). As expected, the energy production increased by up to 60K PJ in S1 to account for projected increase in demand in S1 (figure 6(a)). Also, built up land and agriculture land component replaced forest land to account for increased food demand (figure 6 (b, c and d)). Water demand also shows increased in S1, partly due to higher public water demand input in model and rest due to water requirement for crops. Agricultural imports in wheat and soya were also reflected in model, discussed later in section 4.

3.3. Energy Decentralisation: Rooftop Solar:

The rooftop solar (S2) scenario was created on top of urbanisation scenario. As shown in figure 3, an existing capacity of 10 GW is compounded with 10% YoY growth. The energy production comparison shows that solar and coal has replaced nuclear fuel and biomass (figure 7(a)). This has also resulted in decreased energy costs (Figure 7(b)).

S1 - BAU

Figure 6. Difference between S1 (Urbanisation) and base case (BAU) is plotted for (a) energy production (b) overall land use (c) irrigated land (d) Rainfed land use and (d) water demand.

Figure 7. Difference between S2 (rooftop solar) scenario and S1 (urbanisation) for (a) energy production and (b) energy costs respectively.

****4. Discussion:**

Following insights can be drawn from the results observed in section 3.

1. Base case (BAU):

- a. India's energy demand is already large, about 7% of electricity demand of the world, and is expected to grow at 7% YoY. This means that significant investment in energy sector is needed. Investment in renewables as predicted in the model, along with nuclear, will also align well with India's Net Zero 2070 vision (Figure 4(a)) [8].
- b. The model outputs high capital costs and high overall energy costs due primarily to contribution from nuclear. It is noted that high operational life for nuclear power also contributed to greater slice of nuclear power in energy mix. Feasibility of such greater nuclear power at higher price needs to be evaluated (Figure 4(b and c)).
- c. The food and water demand is also expected to grow two fold and four fold, respectively (Figure 5(a and b)). However, per acre yields in India are below average for most crops including wheat [10]. This means that there is significant room to alleviate pressure from land and water resources [9].

2. Urbanisation (S1):

- a. Higher energy needs in S1 are fulfilled by all low carbon sources namely nuclear, hydro and solar. This means that India is well placed to net zero transition 2070, despite higher demand, provided timely investments in renewable sector (Figure 6(a)).
- b. Due to rapid urbanisation, the agricultural production is peaked in year 2065 (Figure 8). As a result, crops need to be imported to cater to fully cater demand until year 2070. Large contribution of irrigated land in model (Figure 6(c)) also points to need for investments in irrigation technologies. It is likely that this is a result of aggressive urbanisation modelled in S1 coupled with minimum constraint set on forest land of 35%. However, the results point to need to improve yields per Ha. The interconnectedness of energy, land and water systems means that balance needs to be maintained in all three areas for sustainable net zero transition.

3. Energy decentralisation through rooftop solar (S2):

- a. Most of the excess electricity production generated in S1 supplied by nuclear is now catered by solar power in S2 (Figure 7(a)). This has not only implications for cleaner environment (reduced nuclear waste) but also reduced energy costs (Figure 7(b)). However, a comparison of S2 with BAU suggests that nuclear power still has a significant role in providing energy for accelerated demand scenarios (Figure 9).

Figure 8. Agriculture production peaked for urbanisation scenario in 2065 and stays constant thereafter until 2070.

Figure 9. Domestic energy production difference between S2 and BAU. Nuclear power and coal are largest contributors.

4. Model limitations:

- a. It is noted that due to the scale and size of India, most of the data used here is somewhat coarse, although representative. Inclusion of granular

representation of all power, water and land data is important for detailed analysis and to subsequently inform policy.

- b. The model does not consider many renewable technologies such as offshore wind, nuclear fusion etc. Inclusion of these would be important for reasonable prediction of long-term prediction (2050-2070).
 - c. Finally, extraneous factors such as the government policies (both state and centre), GDP growth fluctuation, possible population decline will all have implications for long term projections, currently not factored in model.
5. Future work: Following future work would be important to further development of CLEWs model for India-
- a. Estimation of increase in urban energy demand with built up area Food demand assessment with urbanisation.
 - b. Historical correlation between urbanisation on Agricultural land, forest, other land
 - c. Assessment of potential for solar rooftop.
 - d. Impact of solar rooftop on energy inclusion of areas not connected to grid.

5. Conclusion:

In conclusion, CLEWS based model for India was developed and two scenarios - (1) Urbanisation and (2) Energy decentralisation through rooftop solar. Urbanisation scenario pointed to increased strain on energy, land and water resources while rooftop scenario offered potential alternative to nuclear to alleviate energy costs. Based on this study, following policy actions are recommended-

1. Invest in agricultural technologies to improve yields, irrigation technologies for optimum use of water
2. Deploy rooftop solar aggressively to mitigate future energy costs.

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